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Factors Affecting Enrollment Decisions to Transfer to St. Dominic College of Asia: Basis in the Development of Transferee Evaluation and Needs Analysis Form

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Abstract

This study aimed to assess factors affecting the enrollment decisions of students who have transferred to St. Dominic College of Asia. A total of 103 students participated in the study. Respondents were asked to rate each factor such as family reason, financial reason, social isolation is high, low quality of education, and level of general dissatisfaction. General results showed that family reasons are very high, high financial problems, high social isolation, low quality of education and high dissatisfaction. This would mean that issues in the family, education costs, socialization, poor quality of education and high dissatisfactions are factors why they have left their previous school and transferred to St. Dominic College of Asia.

Keywords: *family reason, financial reason, social isolation, quality of education, general dissatisfaction*

Introduction

Students experience school transfers for many reasons as the generations change. There have been instances where students have transferred throughout their time in college because they are unsure of the program or establishment that will be most helpful to them in finding employment. Regardless of the year they are in, having doubts frequently causes students to transfer to alternative colleges. As they adjust to their new surroundings, transfer students go through additional experiences. When providing support to transfer students, institutions are frequently less prepared than regular students (Matthews, 2015).

This study sought to comprehend transfer students' problems and how they related to their enrollment decisions and other factors influencing their transfer to St. Dominic College of Asia. There have been numerous transfer students in many different institutions. The subject gathers data on social contact and how it affects pupils' behavior and growth in their newly introduced environment. The purpose of the study is to assist students in swiftly adjusting to the institutions by determining the relationship between these variables.

The dynamics of the class may be frequently disrupted by a new student since transfer students encounter different challenges adjusting to and dealing with their new surroundings. Transferees from other locations frequently experience this kind of thing. The primary objective of this research is to identify and analyze the relationships between the variables that can influence a student's decision to transfer to St. Dominic College of Asia.

The term "transferee" refers to students who began their college careers at one institution, earned some course credit there, and then made the decision to transfer to another. Transfer students may have to submit documents in order to be admitted. Additionally, the rules and regulations of their new school will be explained to them. A student may switch colleges for a variety of reasons. They may do so because of the distance, in an effort to be nearer to their family, or as a result of financial constraints. Additionally, transfer students come from a variety of cultural backgrounds and learning styles.

Students may require assistance developing peer relationships while transferring to a new college, which could take some time. For them, the transfer represents a long-term academic and financial objective. Making the decision to transfer to a school is a big one. Transferees may think about transferring if they are unsure of their decision or feel that their original school is no longer the best fit for them. In some cases, people's goals and preferences may change, making the institution they chose years ago seem out of place. Other times, the student has no choice but to transfer because of immovable circumstances.

Each higher educational institution, like St. Dominic College of Asia, has something distinctive to offer in terms of its curriculum and services. Transferees can require assistance transitioning to a new school. However, for new classmates and friends, it might be a crucial factor in their success. According to several studies (Sedahmed & Noureldien, 2019; Draisey, 2016; Ambarova & Shabrova, 2020; He & Giuliano, 2018), students transfer to new schools for a variety of reasons, such as their family's needs, their financial situation, their social isolation, the quality of their education, and their overall contentment.

First, some students have to relocate to attend a university because they have family obligations, including looking after a sick parent or relative. Family obligations can sometimes be enmeshed with financial concerns. Moving to a less expensive institution closer to home may be the sole alternative, for instance, if a parent loses their job and is unable to support their children.

Second, a change in the family's finances, such as losing one's job, an unexpected debt, or the relocation of one or more family members, calls for intricate financial planning. To save money, the student could choose to attend a less expensive institution or relocate closer to home. It has a big role in determining whether students finish college. Transferees are careful to do their homework when looking for a different school and options for financial aid. The cost of finishing is a distinct subject from the price of tuition.

Third, students feel unwelcome at the institution to which they were admitted. They might believe the institution would be a better fit for them if the academic demands were less rigorous or the course options were more diverse. Students usually feel uneasy at first in new situations, especially when everyone is a stranger in a social environment, like culture shock (Whang et al., 2017). They might worry about the faculty, students, community, environment, and standards. It's possible that students' social circumstances have a bigger impact than they realize. In the absence of friends, it may be too much to feel alone.

Fourth, receiving a top-notch education is one of the most important criteria for changing institutions (Ambarova & Shabrova, 2020). In addition to choosing a flexible curriculum that meets their needs and qualifies them for their future employment, students should make sure that the institution is well-known, reputable, and meets the requirements of hiring managers. Students may think about changing schools if they feel that their current institution needs to offer a better education or a stronger curriculum. The institution's accreditation guarantees that it provides top-notch programs taught by reputable leaders and professors and that it is committed to the academic success of its students. Since institutions and programs with this certification are required to meet and maintain certain standards established by national accrediting organizations, it is an important indicator of a high-quality education.

Fifth, as they move forward, students choose—and sometimes even change—their major in accordance with their preferences and sense of general fulfillment. However, not every college offers the same majors or depth of instruction in every subject. Consequently, this is one of the main reasons why students transfer.

The research looked at the elements influencing students' decisions to transfer to St. Dominic College of Asia. The aims of the study are to (1) identify the perceived level of decision-making regarding transferring to St. Dominic College of Asia based on various factors, including family considerations, financial situation, social isolation, educational quality, and general satisfaction; (2) distinguish between factors in enrollment decision to transfer at St. Dominic College of Asia; and (3) identify the relationship between various factors affecting enrollment decisions. Additional research was required on the elements influencing transfer schools in the Philippines, particularly St. Dominic College of Asia. In order to explain the factors impacting students' decisions to transfer to St. Dominic College of Asia, the researchers advised that additional research is necessary. To aid in the development of knowledge about the factors influencing students' decisions to transfer, researchers gathered statistical data. The results of the current study helped to improve knowledge of transfer students' experiences when selecting their courses.

Research Questions

The researchers sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of respondents when they are grouped according to:
 - 1.1. Sex
 - 1.2. Year Level
 - 1.3. School
2. What is the level of the following perceived reasons why they have transferred to St. Dominic College of Asia?
 - 2.1. Family Reason
 - 2.2. Financial Reason
 - 2.3. Social Isolation Reason
 - 2.4. Quality of Education
 - 2.5. General Satisfaction
3. Was there a significant correlation among the aforementioned reasons why they transferred to St. Dominic College of Asia?

Methodology

Research Design

A correlational research design was utilized in the study. This is referred to as a sort of non-experimental research methodology in which a researcher examines two variables, comprehends and evaluates their statistical relationship without the impact of any additional variables, and then reports his findings. This method examines the variables influencing college transfer students' decision to enroll at St. Dominic College of Asia by employing a self-reported questionnaire. There was no trickery going on. The goal of the current study was to see if certain traits could be used to predict whether a student would enroll at or transfer to another college.

Respondents

The table shows the profiling of respondents. For the demographic profile, out of 103 respondents, 31 or 30 percent are male respondents, and 72 or 70 percent are female respondents. For year level, 38 or 37 percent are first year students, 36 or 35 percent of the respondents are second year students, 18 or 17 percent are third year students, and 11 or 11 percent are fourth year students. For school, 21 or 20 percent of the respondents are students from School of Arts, Sciences, and Education, 34 or 33 percent of the respondents are students from School of Business and Computer Studies, 3 or 3 percent of the respondents are students from School of International Hospitality and Tourism Management, 25 or 24 percent of the respondents are students from School of Medical Laboratory Science, and 20 or 20 percent of the respondents are students from School of Nursing and Allied Health Sciences.

Table 1. *Demographic Profile of Respondents*

Demographic Profile		Frequency	Percent
Sex	Male	31	30
	Female	72	70
	Total	103	100.00
Year Level	First	38	37
	Second	36	35
	Third	18	17
	Fourth	11	11
	Total	103	100.00
School	Arts, Sciences and Education	21	20
	Business and Computer Studies	34	33
	International Tourism and Hospitality Management	3	3
	Medical Laboratory Science	25	24
	Nursing and Allied Health Sciences	20	20
Total		103	100.00

Instrument

A self-made questionnaire in the form of a Google Survey was utilized as the research tool in the current study. A series of statements were evaluated on a Likert scale to determine why students decided to transfer. These statements were classified into five categories, including family reasons. Financial, social isolation, quality of education, and general satisfaction experiences of a student. The instrument was permitted to obtain valid responses from the respondents. Their responses would be kept private, and the researchers would only use the responses for discussion purposes as statistical information. Once the respondents were chosen and agreed to participate, informed consent was given and signed. Prior to distributing the Google survey forms, the researchers sought the assistance of a few chosen validators to ensure that the research instrument was accurate.

Procedure

The researchers' choice of data collection was survey type in a Google Form, which has self-made statements or questionnaires. The merits of utilizing such an instrument where it is an easy tool to collect data efficiently and can be distributed faster.

After ensuring that the researchers could survey the target participants to gather information, the researchers designed and obtained approval from the research adviser for the questionnaires they used and had them validated before usage. After being validated by their research adviser and other validators, the researchers obtained a list of transferee students from the DSAS Office, including each participant's email address. They emailed the participants with a link to the Google Forms survey questionnaire wherein they were asked to respond and participate in the study. The survey included a description of the research study as well as its purpose. Lastly, the researchers emphasized that their data and privacy were protected and kept confidential even after the study was completed.

Data Analysis

The following statistical treatment of data was used to answer the following questions and to test the hypothesis of the study.

Frequency Distribution was utilized to obtain the graphical depiction of the sample size depending on the respondents' demographic profiles.

T-test was used to get the graphical representation of the number of respondents based on the respondents' gender.

Anova was used to get the graphical representation of the number of respondents, year level, program and school.

Results and Discussion

SOP 2: What is the level of the following perceived reasons why they have transferred to St. Dominic College of Asia: Family Reason, Financial Reason, Social Isolation Reason, Quality of Education, General Satisfaction

The table above shows the mean score for family reasons as to why they have transferred to St. Dominic College of Asia. Respondents who are male, first year and fourth year college students, and students who are from the School of International Hospitality and Tourism Management and School of Nursing and Allied Health Sciences obtained a mean score within 3.40 to 4.19, which is verbally described as "Agree" and interpreted as "High Family Reasons". The remaining sub-levels of the demographic profile obtained mean scores within 4.20-5.00, which is verbally described as "Strongly Agree" and interpreted as "Very High Family Reasons."

The overall mean score for the family reason as to why they have transferred to St. Dominic College of Asia is 4.24, which is verbally described as Strongly Agree and interpreted as "Very High Family Reasons."

Table 2. Mean Score for Family as Reason of Transfer

Demographic Profile		Mean	Verbal Description	Verbal Interpretation
Sex	Male	4.13	Agree	High family reason
	Female	4.28	Strongly Agree	Very high family reason
	Average	4.24	Strongly Agree	Very high family reason
Year Level	First	4.11	Agree	High family reason
	Second	4.31	Strongly Agree	Very high family reason
	Third	4.44	Strongly Agree	Very high family reason
	Fourth	4.10	Agree	High family reason
	Average	4.24	Strongly Agree	Very high family reason
School	Arts, Sciences and Education	4.27	Strongly Agree	Very high family reason
	Business and Computer Studies	4.23	Strongly Agree	Very high family reason
	International Tourism and Hospitality Management	3.67	Agree	High family reason
	Medical Laboratory Science	4.49	Strongly Agree	Very high family reason
	Nursing and Allied Health Sciences	3.98	Agree	High family reason
	Average	4.24	Strongly Agree	Very high family reason

Legend: 4.20-5.00= Strongly Agree; 3.40-4.19= Agree; 2.60-3.39= Neutral; 1.80-2.59= Disagree; 1.00-1.79= Strongly Disagree

According to Serrata, et al. (2019), the findings indicate that families have an impact on the students' "choice sets" and play a complicated role in providing inspiration, emotional, informational, and financial support, among other things.

Table 3. Mean Score for Financial as Reason of Transfer

Demographic Profile		Mean	Verbal Description	Verbal Interpretation
Sex	Male	4.08	Agree	High financial problem
	Female	4.17	Agree	High financial problem
	Average	4.14	Agree	High financial problem
Year Level	First	4.03	Agree	High financial problem
	Second	4.19	Agree	High financial problem
	Third	4.36	Strongly Agree	Very high financial problem
	Fourth	4.03	Agree	High financial problem
Average	4.14	Agree	High financial problem	
School	Arts, Sciences and Education	4.15	Agree	High financial problem
	Business and Computer Studies	4.15	Agree	High financial problem
	International Tourism and Hospitality Management	3.43	Agree	High financial problem
	Medical Laboratory Science	4.42	Strongly Agree	Very high financial problem
	Nursing and Allied Health Sciences	3.89	Agree	High financial problem
	Average	4.14	Agree	High financial problem

Legend: 4.20-5.00= Strongly Agree; 3.40-4.19= Agree; 2.60-3.39= Neutral; 1.80-2.59= Disagree; 1.00-1.79= Strongly Disagree

The table above shows the mean score for financial problems as to why they transferred to St. Dominic College of Asia. Respondents who are third year students and students who are from the School of Medical Laboratory Science obtained a mean score of 4.42 which is verbally described as “Strongly Agree” and interpreted as “Very High Financial Problem.” The rest of the sub-levels of each demographic profile obtained a mean score within 3.40-4.19 which is verbally described as agree and verbally interpreted as “High Financial Problem.”

The overall mean score for financial problem as to why they transferred to St. Dominic College of Asia is 4.14 which is verbally described as “Agree” and interpreted as “High Financial Problem.”

According to Trevor (2016), 85-90 percent of students receive financial assistance. The study discovered that a student's school choice is influenced by the cost, significant family, and availability of the desired course. Tuition support enhances the likelihood that a student will attend school according to Sycamore University.

The table 4 shows the mean score for social isolation as to why they transferred to St. Dominic College of Asia. Respondents who are third year students and students who are from the School of Medical Laboratory Science obtained a mean score of 4.32 which is

verbally described as “Strongly Agree” and interpreted as “Very High Social Isolation.” The rest of the sub-levels of each demographic profile obtained a mean score within 3.40-4.19 which is verbally described as agree and verbally interpreted as “High Social Isolation.”

Table 4. Mean Score for Social Isolation as Reason of Transfer

Demographic Profile		Mean	Verbal Description	Verbal Interpretation
Sex	Male	3.98	Agree	High social isolation
	Female	4.09	Agree	High social isolation
	Average	4.06	Agree	High social isolation
Year Level	First	3.95	Agree	High social isolation
	Second	4.10	Agree	High social isolation
	Third	4.31	Strongly Agree	Very high social isolation
	Fourth	3.88	Agree	High social isolation
	Average	4.06	Agree	High social isolation
School	Arts, Sciences and Education	4.08	Agree	High social isolation
	Business and Computer Studies	4.05	Agree	High social isolation
	International Tourism and Hospitality Management	3.50	Agree	High social isolation
	Medical Laboratory Science	4.32	Strongly Agree	Very high social isolation
	Nursing and Allied Health Sciences	3.80	Agree	High social isolation
	Average	4.06	Agree	High social isolation

Legend: 4.20-5.00= Strongly Agree; 3.40-4.19= Agree; 2.60-3.39= Neutral; 1.80-2.59= Disagree; 1.00-1.79= Strongly Disagree

The overall mean score for social isolation as to why they transferred to St. Dominic College of Asia is 4.06 which is verbally described as “Agree” and interpreted as “High Social Isolation.”

According to Lu and Tsotsong (2020), being socially isolated drives students to become detached from the school community and distanced from the institution.

Table 5. Mean Score for Quality of Education as Reason of Transfer

Demographic Profile		Mean	Verbal Description	Verbal Interpretation
Sex	Male	3.94	Agree	Low quality of education
	Female	4.02	Agree	Low quality of education
	Average	4.00	Agree	Low quality of education
Year Level	First	3.89	Agree	Low quality of education
	Second	4.08	Agree	Low quality of education
	Third	4.23	Strongly Agree	Very low quality of education
	Fourth	3.72	Agree	Low quality of education
	Average	4.00	Agree	Low quality of education
School	Arts, Sciences and Education	3.96	Agree	Low quality of education
	Business and Computer Studies	4.01	Agree	Low quality of education
	International Tourism and Hospitality Management	3.37	Neutral	Uncertain
	Medical Laboratory Science	4.31	Strongly Agree	Very low quality of education
	Nursing and Allied Health Sciences	3.73	Agree	Low quality of education
	Average	4.00	Agree	Low quality of education

Legend: 4.20-5.00= Strongly Agree; 3.40-4.19= Agree; 2.60-3.39= Neutral; 1.80-2.59= Disagree; 1.00-1.79= Strongly Disagree

The table above shows the mean score for perceived quality education as the reason why they transferred to St. Dominic College of Asia. Based on the results, respondents who are third year students and students from the School of Medical Laboratory Science obtained a mean score of 4.20 to 5.00, which is verbally described as “Strongly Agree” and interpreted as “Very Low Quality Education.” Respondents who are from the School of International Tourism and Hospitality Management obtained a mean score of 3.37 which is verbally described as “Neutral” and interpreted as “Uncertain if the quality of education is low or not ”.

The remaining sub-levels of each demographic profile obtained mean scores within 3.40-4.19, which is verbally described as “Agree” and interpreted as “Low Quality of Education”.

The overall mean score for quality of education as the reason why they have transferred to St. Dominic College of Asia is 4.00, which is verbally described as “Agree” and interpreted as “Low Quality of Education”

According to Ching et al. (2021), there has been a limited study focused on the quality of education components of different schools in Asia. It is claimed that, in contrast to Western institutions, certain Asian schools are unprepared to assist transfer students in integrating into their new environment, which leads to students transferring to another school.

Table 6. Mean Score for General Dissatisfaction as Reason of Transfer

Demographic Profile		Mean	Verbal Description	Verbal Interpretation
Sex	Male	4.03	Agree	Highly dissatisfied
	Female	4.00	Agree	Highly dissatisfied
	Average	4.01	Agree	Highly dissatisfied
Year Level	First	3.96	Agree	Highly dissatisfied
	Second	4.06	Agree	Highly dissatisfied
	Third	4.18	Agree	Highly dissatisfied
	Fourth	3.74	Agree	Highly dissatisfied
	Average	4.01	Agree	Highly dissatisfied
School	Arts, Sciences and Education	3.94	Agree	Highly dissatisfied
	Business and Computer Studies	4.04	Agree	Highly dissatisfied
	International Tourism and Hospitality Management	3.33	Neutral	Highly dissatisfied
	Medical Laboratory Science	4.27	Strongly Agree	Very Highly dissatisfied
	Nursing and Allied Health Sciences	3.80	Agree	Highly dissatisfied
	Average	4.01	Agree	Highly dissatisfied

Legend: 4.20-5.00= Strongly Agree; 3.40-4.19= Agree; 2.60-3.39= Neutral; 1.80-2.59= Disagree; 1.00-1.79= Strongly Disagree

The table above shows the mean score for general dissatisfaction as a reason why they have transferred to St. Dominic College of Asia. Based on the results, respondents from the School of Medical Laboratory Sciences obtained a mean score of 4.27 which is verbally described as strongly agreed and interpreted as “Very Highly Dissatisfied”. The remaining sub-levels of each demographic profile obtained mean scores within 3.40 to 4.19, which is verbally described as “Agree” and interpreted as “Highly Dissatisfied.”

The overall mean score for general dissatisfaction as the reason why they have transferred to St. Dominic College of Asia is 4.01, which is verbally described as “Agree” and interpreted as “Highly Dissatisfied”

According to Trevor (2016), general satisfaction, such as having several programs in assisting tuition fees and others in an institution, helps students be encouraged to enroll in the school.

Table 7. Correlation Among Reasons of Transfer

Correlated Factors		r-value	Interpretation	P-value	Significance	Ho Decision
Family	Financial	.960 ^{**}	Very High Positive Correlation	0.000	Significant	Reject
	Social isolation	.914 ^{**}	Very High Positive Correlation	0.000	Significant	Reject
	Quality of Education	.846 ^{**}	High Positive Correlation	0.000	Significant	Reject
	General Satisfaction	.762 ^{**}	High Positive Correlation	0.000	Significant	Reject
Financial	Social isolation	.963 ^{**}	Very High Positive Correlation	0.000	Significant	Reject
	Quality of Education	.911 ^{**}	Very High Positive Correlation	0.000	Significant	Reject
	General Satisfaction	.859 ^{**}	High Positive Correlation	0.000	Significant	Reject
Social Isolation	Quality of Education	.969 ^{**}	Very High Positive Correlation	0.000	Significant	Reject
	General Satisfaction	.921 ^{**}	Very High Positive Correlation	0.000	Significant	Reject
Quality of Education	General Satisfaction	.967 ^{**}	Very High Positive Correlation	0.000	Significant	Reject

** Significant at .05 level

The table above shows the correlation among factors or reasons why they have transferred to St. Dominic College of Asia. For family reasons correlated with financial reasons, the R-value is 0.960, which is interpreted as a "Very High Positive Correlation" with a P-value of 0.00 which is less than the .05 alpha level. This would mean that there is a significant correlation, and the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence, as family problems increase, financial concerns or problems also increase.

For family reasons correlated with social isolation reasons, the R-value is 0.914, which is interpreted as a "Very High Positive Correlation" with a P-value of 0.00 which is less than the .05 alpha level. This would mean that there is a significant correlation, and the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence, as family problems increase, social isolation also increases.

For family reasons correlated with quality of education, the R-value is 0.846, which is interpreted as a "High Positive Correlation" with a P-value of 0.00 which is less than the .05 alpha level. This would mean that there is a significant correlation, and the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence, as the family problem increases, the perceived low quality of education also increases.

For family reasons correlated with general satisfaction, the R-value is 0.762, interpreted as a "High Positive Correlation" with a P-value of 0.00 which is less than the .05 alpha level. This would mean that there is a significant correlation, and the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence, as family problems increase, perceived low satisfaction also increases.

For financial reasons correlated with social isolation, the R-value is 0.963, which is interpreted as a "Very High Positive Correlation" with a P-value of 0.00 which is less than the .05 alpha level. This would mean that there is a significant correlation, and the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence, as financial problems increase, social isolation also increases.

For financial reasons correlated with the quality of education, the R-value is 0.911, which is interpreted as a "Very High Positive Correlation" with a P-value of 0.00 which is less than the .05 alpha level. This would mean that there is a significant correlation and null hypothesis is rejected. Hence, as financial problems increase, the perceived low quality of education also increases.

For financial reasons correlated with general satisfaction, the R-value is 0.859, which is interpreted as a "High Positive Correlation" with a P-value of 0.00 which is less than the .05 alpha level. This would mean that there is a significant correlation, and the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence, as financial problems increase, perceived low satisfaction also increases.

For social isolation reasons correlated with quality of education reason, the R-value is 0.969, which is interpreted as a "Very High Positive Correlation" with a P-value of 0.00 which is less than the .05 alpha level. This would mean that there is a significant correlation, and the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence, as social isolation increases, the perceived low quality of education also increases.

For social isolation reasons correlated with general satisfaction, the R-value is 0.921, which is interpreted as a "Very High Positive Correlation" with a P-value of 0.00 which is less than the .05 alpha level. This would mean that there is a significant correlation, and the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence, as social isolation increases, perceived low satisfaction also increases.

For quality of education reasons correlated with general satisfaction, the R-value is 0.967, which is interpreted as a "Very High Positive Correlation" with a P-value of 0.00 which is less than the .05 alpha level. This would mean that there is a significant correlation, and the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence, as perceived low quality education increases, perceived low satisfaction also increases.

The term "student transfer and mobility" refers to any change in a student's institution of enrolment, regardless of when, where, or how the move occurred. It also refers to whether any credits were transferred from one institution to another. The transfer rate reported here takes into account a student's first relocation to a different institution, which must occur within six years after getting a bachelor's degree and before graduation. We also include transfers that took place after a student earned a degree at the initial two-year college for those students who started at public two-year institutions. This research explores the distribution of transfers and mobility across state lines and across a number of years, as well as student enrollment patterns among two-year and four-year, public and private institutions. This research contains transfer trends broken down by race and ethnicity for the first time. This will reveal how students from historically underrepresented groups navigate the pipeline relative to their peers and offer insight into how different groups of students progress through post-secondary education (Doug et al, 2018).

Brian, et al. (2019) stated that family plays a significant influence on the educational aspect of their family members as the fundamental unit of society. Although problems are unavoidable, a student's behavior or academic performance may be impacted by their inability to manage them. Family issues, including money issues, marital issues, and poor habits, are significant factors in the pupils' performance. The student's attendance and compliance with the assignments and activities at school are impacted by a lack of financial support. Instead of going hungry one day in class, students decide not to attend.

On the other hand, the student's emotional state is influenced by family relationships. It affects their ability to focus in class. Students develop negative habits and behaviors due to their families' incorrect cultural practices. Family issues are unavoidable and have a significant negative impact on student's academic achievement.

Conclusions

There is no significant difference between the factors influencing transfer decisions to St. Dominic College of Asia when respondents are grouped according to their demographic profile. However, there is a significant correlation between the aforementioned factors.

When students are deciding whether to transfer to another school or stay, the factors mentioned earlier play a role.

Based on the result, the five factors, family reasons, financial problems, social isolation, quality of education, and general dissatisfaction, are correlated to each other in affecting the decision of a student to transfer to institutions.

Based on this, it concludes that these factors are reasons why students leave their previous school, and it can also be used as a basis for developing intervention programs for transfer students so that they can easily integrate themselves into their new environment.

Recommendations

Students. The researchers encourage students to communicate with the school if there are issues that could lead to them transferring to other institutions.

Teachers. The researchers advise teachers that communication with students and parents is essential. If you notice that the student is having difficulties, connect with them and ask them if there is anything they can do to assist them. These items can enhance the student's experience with the school and encourage them to stay.

Institution. The researchers strongly advise the institution to implement intervention programs for transfer students to help them integrate into their new environment and prevent them from switching again, which would drastically reduce St. Dominic College of Asia's transfer rate.

Future Researchers. The researchers recommend that future researchers include the respondent's previous school in the demographic profile for further research between different institutions and to determine if there is a significant relationship between the previous university's profile and the students' transferring decision. Furthermore, the researchers strongly recommend integrating additional factors not stated in the study for additional information on the correlation of variables that may affect students' decision to transfer to a specific institution and to design more intervention measures. The researchers also advise conducting extensive face-to-face data collection. This will ensure that the participants comprehend the study completely.

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